

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF

ENGINEERING MATHEMATICS: THEORY AND APPLICATION

Indexed by:

Universal
Impact Factor

IMPACT FACTOR
SEARCH

Editorial Team

G. Ahmed

Professor of Computational Engineering

Mathematics and Numerical Analysis

Department of Engineering Physics and Mathematics

Associate editor-in-Chief

Dr. Hamed Daei Kasmaei

PhD in Applied mathematics-Numerical analysis and computational

Department of Mathematics and Statistics,

Honor President of IEEMS

Mahim Ranjan Adhikari

Department of Mathematics

Calcutta University

India

Carlo Cattani Professor, Tuscia University, Viterbo

Department of Economy and Enterprise DEIM

Italy E-mail: ccattani@unisa.it

Dr. Sunil Kumar National Institute of Technology

Jamshedpur Department of Mathematics

India Email: skitbhu28@gmail.com

Praveen Agarwal

Ph.D., Professor

Anand International College of Engineering

Department of Mathematics Jaipur India

Email: goyal.praveen2011@gmail.com

Thomas Korimort Mathematician

Computer Scientist Dr. tech. Dipl.-Ing

AMS University of Leoben Vienna University of

Technology Austria Email: tomkori@gmx.net

Dr. Stephen Kirkup

Lecturer in Nuclear Science / Engineering

School of Engineering Computing and Technology

Building, CM138 University of Central Lancashire

United Kingdom Email: smkirkup@uclan.ac.uk

Dr Mehmet Senol

Nevsehir Haci Bektas Veli University Department of

Mathematics Nev_sehir

Turkey

Email: msenol@nevsehir.edu.tr

Dr. Muhammad Sadiq Hashmi

Associate Professor

Department of Computer Science

COMSATS Institute of Information Technology

Sahiwal Campus Pakistan

Email: sadiq.hashmi@gmail.com

Hector Vazquez Leal

Full Time Professor

School of Electronic Instrumentation

University of Veracruz

Mexico Email: hvazquez@uv.mx

Dr. Jyotindra C. Prajapati

M.Sc., M. Phil., Ph.D., MIMS, MISTE

Principal, Faculty of Science

Marwadi University

Rajkot-Morbi Highway

RAJKOT- 360003, GUJARAT

India

Hasan Bulut

Faculty of Science Department of Mathematics Firat

University Elazig Turkey

E-mail: hbulut@firat.edu.tr

Fethi Bin Muhammad Belgacem Department of

Mathematics Faculty of Basic Education

PAAET, Al-Ardhiya Kuwait E-

mail: fbmbelgacem@gmail.com

Avishk Mahim Adkhaira

Associate Professor of Mathematics Calcutta

University

India E-mail: math.mra@gmail.com

János Kurdics

Professor of Mathematics University of Nyiregyhaza

Hungary Academic Member of ATINER

Athens E-mail: kurdics@nyf.hu

CONTACT

Professor of Computational Engineering

Mathematics and Numerical Analysis

Faculty of Engineering

Zagazig University

Zagazig

P. O. 44519

Egypt

<http://iejemta.com/>

Email: sgamil@zu.edu.eg

TOOLS OF TACTICAL MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ANALYTICAL METHODS, AND EFFICIENCY ASSESSMENT

T.I.Ibragimov – Independent PhD Researcher, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service (SamIES).

Abstract. The article examines the tools of tactical management of educational services in higher education institutions under the conditions of transformation of the education market. Particular attention is paid to quality management systems, analytical tools for evaluating the effectiveness of educational programs, quantitative methods for monitoring graduate employment, and the integration of digital technologies into the management of educational activities. Based on statistical data from universities in Uzbekistan and international practice, an analytical model for assessing the effectiveness of educational services is proposed. Key performance indicators (KPIs), efficiency calculation formulas, and recommendations for improving the competitiveness of universities are developed.

Keywords: educational services, higher education, tactical management, quality management, university KPIs, graduate employment, digitalization of education, benchmarking.

Relevance of the research. The development of the higher education system under modern conditions is characterized by increasing competition among universities, growing labor market requirements for the quality of specialist training, digitalization of educational processes, and the globalization of educational markets. These factors require the improvement of methods for managing educational services, primarily at the tactical level.

Analysis of the literature used. F. Kotler and K. Fox studied the application of strategic marketing in the field of education, considering educational institutions as participants in a competitive market of educational services and analyzing methods for increasing their competitiveness [2].

The OECD organization, in its annual analytical report *Education at a Glance*, examines international indicators of the effectiveness of educational systems, including the impact of education on employment, income, and economic development [5].

The UNESCO organization, in the report *Global Education Monitoring Report*, analyzes global trends in the development of education, issues of accessibility of educational services, quality of education, and their impact on socio-economic development [6].

I. Ansoff studied the strategic aspects of organizational management, developing concepts of strategic planning and management that are also applied in the management system of educational organizations. S.M. Vdovin, T.A. Salimova, and L.I. Biryukova studied quality management systems in organizations, including methods for implementing quality standards and assessing the effectiveness of management processes [1;3].

Russian studies in the field of quality management also emphasize the standardization of management processes, internal audit, and improving the efficiency of organizational activities, including educational institutions.

U.S. Nadirkhanov studied modern trends in the development of the higher education system in Uzbekistan, focusing on institutional reforms and the modernization of educational programs. I.U. Nematov analyzed the formation of marketing strategies in the market of educational services in Uzbekistan and issues of improving the competitiveness of universities. B.I. Ismoilova studied reforms in the higher education system of Uzbekistan aimed at increasing access to education, developing innovations, and expanding opportunities for youth [8;9;10].

Research Methodology

The methodological basis of the research is formed by systemic and institutional approaches to the analysis of the management of educational services in higher education institutions. In the course of the research, methods of comparative and statistical analysis, economic and analytical methods for evaluating the effectiveness of educational programs, as well as strategic analysis tools (KPI analysis, benchmarking, and SWOT analysis) were used. The empirical base of the research consisted of statistical data from higher education institutions in Uzbekistan, materials from international organizations, and the results of scientific research in the field of education quality management.

Analysis and Results

Tactical management of educational services represents a system of medium-term managerial decisions aimed at implementing the strategic goals of a university through the optimization of educational programs, improvement of teaching quality, and efficient use of resources.

Particular importance is given to:

- education quality management systems;
- analytical tools for monitoring performance;
- quantitative methods for assessing learning outcomes;
- integration of digital management technologies.

The purpose of the article is to develop a comprehensive analytical approach to the toolkit of tactical management of university educational services, taking into account the practices of universities in Uzbekistan.

1. Theoretical Foundations of Tactical Management of Educational Services

Educational services represent a specific type of socio-economic activity characterized by several features:

1. intangible nature of the result;
2. long duration of provision;
3. dependence of quality on the interaction between teacher and student;
4. social significance;
5. a high share of intellectual labor.

Tactical management in the higher education system performs the following functions:

- implementation of strategic educational programs;
- adaptation of curricula to labor market requirements;
- management of the quality of the educational process;
- control of the financial efficiency of educational programs.

In the context of the growing number of students in Uzbekistan (more than 1.3–1.4 million students in recent years), the burden on education quality management systems is increasing, as well as the need to introduce modern management tools.

2. Quality Management Systems as a Tool of Tactical Management

2.1 Essence of Education Quality Management Systems

Quality management systems (QMS) in higher education are aimed at ensuring that educational services comply with established quality standards.

The main elements of QMS include:

- internal audits of educational programs;– accreditation of educational programs;
- monitoring student satisfaction;
- standardization of educational processes;
- control of learning outcomes.

The international basis for QMS is represented by the ISO 9000 series standards adapted to the educational sector.

2.2 Economic Efficiency of QMS Implementation

The economic effect of a quality system can be evaluated using the formula:

$$Eq = (B - C) / C$$

where:

B — additional income or savings resulting from quality improvement;
 C — costs of implementing the quality management system.

Example:

costs of implementing QMS — 150 thousand USD; increase in revenue from higher student enrollment — 280 thousand USD.

$$Eq = (280 - 150) / 150 = 0.87$$

Thus, the efficiency of implementation amounted to 87%.

Table 1

Elements of the Quality Management System in a University¹

Element	Content	Result
Internal audit	Control of educational processes	Reduction of errors
Accreditation	External quality assessment	Increase in trust
Student monitoring	Surveys, feedback	Improvement of learning
Standardization	Regulations, procedures	Improvement of manageability

3. Analytical Tools of Tactical Management

3.1 KPI System of Educational Activities

Key performance indicators make it possible to quantitatively assess the results of university activities.

1. Graduate employment rate

$$E = N_{\text{employed}} / N_{\text{graduates}} \times 100\%$$

In leading universities of Uzbekistan, this indicator reaches 85–95%.

2. Student retention rate

$$R = N_{\text{final}} / N_{\text{initial}} \times 100\%$$

The optimal level is 80–90%.

3. Profitability of an educational program

$$Rp = (Income - Costs) / Costs \times 100\%$$

For sustainable programs, the indicator is 10–25%.

Table 2

Example of KPI Indicators for an Educational Program²

¹ Source: compiled by the author based on the ISO 9001:2015 standards, the recommendations of the European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA), and analytical materials of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Indicator	Value	Evaluation
Employment rate	88%	High level
Student retention rate	84%	Satisfactory
Profitability	18%	Effective
Student satisfaction	4.4/5	High

3.2 Benchmarking of Educational Programs

Benchmarking involves comparing a university's performance indicators with those of leading universities.

Competitiveness Index:

$$CI = P_{uni} / P_{best}$$

If the employment rate at a university is 82%, and at the leading university it is 95%:

$$CI = 0.82 / 0.95 = 0.86$$

This indicates the need to improve the educational program.

3.3 SWOT Analysis of Educational Services

SWOT analysis is used to identify internal and external factors influencing the development of educational programs.

Table 3

SWOT Analysis (Example)³

Strengths	Weaknesses
High qualification of teaching staff	Insufficient digitalization
Developed links with employers	Limited resources
Opportunities	Threats
Growing demand for specialists	Increasing competition
International projects	Demographic decline

4. Econometric Model of the Impact of Education Quality on Graduate Employment

To assess the impact of the quality of educational services on the employment of graduates, a regression model can be applied:

$$Emp = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Q + \beta_2 D + \beta_3 Exp + \varepsilon$$

where:

Emp — graduate employment rate;

² Source: compiled by the author based on statistical data from higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, reports of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as international studies *OECD Education at a Glance* and *World Bank Education Statistics*.

³ Source: compiled by the author based on ISO 9001:2015 standards and ENQA materials.

Q— education quality index;

D — level of digitalization of education;

Exp — practice-oriented nature of the program;

ε — random error.

Interpretation of the model:

- a 1% increase in education quality may increase employment by 0.4–0.6%;
- the introduction of digital technologies increases the competitiveness of graduates;
- practical training has a significant impact on employment.

5. Digital Tools for Managing Educational Services

Key digital tools include:

- LMS platforms for learning management;
- CRM systems for working with applicants;
- educational data analytics;
- online courses and hybrid learning formats.

Practice shows that digitalization makes it possible to:

- reduce administrative costs by 10–15%;
- increase student retention by 8–12%;
- increase student satisfaction.

6. Practical Recommendations for Improving Tactical Management

1. Implementation of an integrated quality management system.
2. Development of analytical systems for KPI monitoring.
3. Strengthening interaction with employers.
4. Expansion of digital educational technologies.
5. Regular benchmarking of educational programs.
6. Development of university career centers.

Conclusion

The toolkit of tactical management of educational services in higher education institutions represents a complex of interconnected methods and instruments, including quality management systems, analytical methods for evaluating efficiency, and digital management technologies.

Effective use of these tools makes it possible to:

- improve the quality of educational programs;
- enhance graduate employment indicators;
- strengthen the competitiveness of universities;
- ensure sustainable development of the higher education system.

Under modern conditions, the integration of quality systems and analytical tools becomes a key factor for the successful functioning of universities.

References

1. Ansoff I. *Strategic Management*. — Moscow: Ekonomika, 1989. — 519 p.

2. Kotler F., Fox K. *Strategic Marketing for Educational Institutions*. — Moscow: Alpina Publisher, 2008. — 464 p.
3. Vdovin S.M., Salimova T.A., Biryukova L.I. *Quality Management System of an Organization: Textbook*. — Moscow: INFRA-M, 2024. — 299 p. — ISBN 978-5-16-019496-7.
4. **ISO 9001:2015** *Quality Management Systems — Requirements*. — Geneva: International Organization for Standardization, 2015. — 29 p.
5. OECD. *Education at a Glance 2024: OECD Indicators*. — Paris: OECD Publishing, 2024.
6. UNESCO. *Global Education Monitoring Report 2023*. — Paris: UNESCO Publishing, 2023.
7. Agency of Statistics under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Volume of Services in the Field of Education: Statistical Review*. — Tashkent, 2025.
8. Nadirkhanov U.S. Higher Education System in the Republic of Uzbekistan: Modern Trends and Developments // *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*. — 2023. — Vol. 6, Issue 3. — P. 1358–1364.
9. Nematov I.U. Development of the Marketing Strategy of the Educational Services Market in Uzbekistan // *Economics and Education*. — 2025. — No. 2.
10. Ismoilova B.I. Reforms in the Higher Education System of Uzbekistan: Broad Opportunities for the Youth of the Country // *Education and Innovations*. — 2024. — No. 3. — P. 45–52.
11. Aslanova D.Kh., Ibragimov T.I. Analysis of Supply in the Higher Education Services Market and Trends in Its Development // *Servis*. — 2025. — No. 3.
12. Ibragimov T.I. Joint Educational Programs as a Factor in Training Specialists in Higher Education of Uzbekistan // *Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference*. — 2024.
13. Ibragimov T.I., Aslanova D.Kh. Application of Interactive Methods in Teaching Economic Sciences and Their Effectiveness // *Collection of Scientific Articles*. — 2024.

